

Controlling the recovery time of the superconducting nanowire single-photon detector with a voltage-controlled cryogenic tunable resistor

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Superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPD), owing to their unique performance, are currently the standard detector in most demanding single-photon experiments. One important metric for any single-photon detector is the deadtime (or recovery time), defined as the minimum temporal separation between consecutive detection events. In SNSPDs, the recovery time is more subtle, as the detection efficiency does not abruptly drop to zero when the temporal separation between detection events gets smaller, instead, it increases gradually as the SNSPD current recovers. SNSPD's recovery time is dominated by its kinetic inductance, the readout impedance, and the degree of saturation of internal efficiency. Decreasing the kinetic inductance or increasing the readout impedance can accelerate the recovery process. Significant reduction of the SNSPD recovery time, by, for example, adding a series resistor in the readout circuitry, is possible but can lead to detector latching which hinders further detector operation or enforces underbiasing and hence a reduction in detection efficiency. Previous research has demonstrated passive resistive networks for the reduction of recovery time that rely on trial and error to find the appropriate resistance values. Here we show, using a novel, cryogenically compatible, and tunable resistor technology, one can find the optimized impedance values, delivering fast SNSPD recovery time, while maintaining maximum internal detection efficiency. Here we show an increase of more than 2 folds in both maximum achievable detection rates and the achievable detection efficiency at high photon fluxes, demonstrating detection rates as high as 120 Mcps with no loss of internal detection efficiency.

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FIG. 1. (a) Schematic representation of electrical equivalent model of a SNSPD with a resistor R_s in series. (b) Simulated output voltage profile with $R_s = 0 \Omega$, 150Ω and 350Ω , respectively. (c) The evolution of the temperature profile of the superconducting nanowire with $R_s = 0 \Omega$, 150Ω and 350Ω , respectively. Details of the simulation parameters can be found in supplementary material section II.

Superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs), composed of superconducting nanowires biased close to their critical currents, have become a cutting-edge technology in single-photon detection.^{1–3} SNSPDs have gained numerous research interests, attributed to their remarkable single photon sensitivity, broad spectral range^{4,5}, high detection efficiency (>95 %^{6–8}), and a low time jitter (tens of picoseconds^{9–11}). There is an increasing demand for SNSPDs in various applications such as biomedical imaging¹², optical communication¹³, and quantum key distribution^{14–16}.

When a photon is absorbed by the SNSPD, a resistive section is formed in the nanowire, which will initially expand due to Joule heating (current passing through a resistor). Subsequently, in an appropriately functioning SNSPD, the current is diverted to the readout, and this resistive section disappears due to the reduction of Joule heating and continuous cooling of the sample. This dynamics in the current redistribution between the SNSPD and the readout electronics leads to an electrical pulse at the output. The resulting output pulse usually rises steeply (sub-nanosecond) and decays slowly (nanoseconds), which is correlated with the inductive time constant L_k/R (L_k is the kinetic inductance of the SNSPD, and R is the resistance in the circuit). Thus, the falling

edge of the output influences the nanowire current recovery time, which is linked to its internal detection efficiency as a result. As the efficiency does not drop and recover abruptly in SNSPDs, the recovery time τ_{rec} can be defined as the time interval required to register a second photon subsequent to an earlier detection event with $\geq 50\%$ internal detection efficiency. This parameter is one of the essential performance metrics for applications that demand higher photon count rates, such as optical communication, or high-throughput optical quantum computing.

SNSPDs have a shorter recovery time when their kinetic inductances are lower. However, this also results in the reduction of the active detection area, which is disadvantageous for optical absorption and hence system detection efficiency. Other approaches to raise detection rates, such as utilizing Quasi-Constant-Voltage (QCV) bias¹⁷, employing the resistive attenuator readout circuit¹⁸, and implementing a DC-coupled readout scheme¹⁹, were demonstrated, but these non-cryogenic solutions have limited performance enhancements as there is a considerable delay (nano-seconds) between the SNSPD and the control circuit. Another more effective way is to introduce a cryogenic serial resistor to SNSPD's readout circuit to reduce the recovery time by increasing R .^{18,20} The value of the serial resistance needs to be carefully optimized to minimize recovery time while avoiding the formation of a stable hotspot in the superconducting nanowire, which is referred to as the latching phenomenon²¹. Based on the analysis of electrothermal effects in SNSPDs, the optimized value for this serial resistance can be influenced by various factors such as the heat transfer coefficient between the superconducting nanowire and the substrate, the geometry of the meandering nanowire, and the material properties of the superconducting layer (sheet resistance, critical current density, biasing current, etc.).²² Therefore, the resistance value is often refined experimentally through a series of trials and errors, which is time-consuming and does not necessarily guarantee optimal performance.

In this work, we demonstrate a cryogenic tunable resistor to tune the serial resistance to the optimal value. The tunable resistor consists of a superconducting channel and a metal heater insulated by a SiO_2 layer. The resistance of the superconducting channel is controlled by the localized heat transfer from the heater and the self-Joule heating of the superconducting channel. This adjustable electrical component operating in cryogenic environments constitutes an efficient strategy to enhance the SNSPD performance at high photon flux rates. We show that this on-chip device is fully compatible with SNSPDs, enabling real-time optimization of the electrical recovery time while maintaining high internal detection efficiency.

Fig. 1 represents a one-dimensional electrothermal simulation as described in Yang *et al.*²¹,

which illustrates the basic principle to decrease the recovery time by connecting a small resistor in series with a SNSPD (More information about the simulation can be found in supplementary material section II). The results were simulated at 2.5 K, which is the base temperature of our cryostat. An equivalent electrical diagram of a SNSPD in series with a resistor R_s is depicted in Fig. 1(a). The SNSPD is biased with a current source I_{bias} and is in parallel with the readout electronics, which is a capacitor C_b and a load resistor $Z_0 = 50 \Omega$, representing the input impedance of an RF amplifier. The simple circuit here, ignores the time delay (corresponding to the transmission lines and the coaxial cables) between the detector and the amplifier. This provides an acceptable approximation as long as the recovery time is longer than the mentioned time delay (normally on the order of a few nanoseconds).

Once a single photon triggers a resistive section across the nanowire, this section quickly expands due to Joule heating and the bias current through the detector I_d is redirected to the load resistor, resulting in the rising edge at the output. The characteristic time of the rising edge is $\tau_1(t) \approx L_k / (Z_0 + R_s + R_L(t))$, where $L_k = 750 \text{ nH}$ and $R_L(t)$ represent the kinetic inductance of the detector and the real-time total hot-spot resistance in our simulation. After the resistive spot disappears via the heat dissipation to the substrate, the current flows back to the SNSPD with the time constant $\tau_2 \approx L_k / (Z_0 + R_s)$, corresponding to the falling edge of the output signal. Since $R_L(t)$ (typically a few $\text{k}\Omega$) significantly exceeds Z_0 and R_s , the pulse duration τ_{out} defined at $1/e$ of the pulse height is dominated by τ_2 .

The simulated output signals with three different R_s values are shown in Fig. 1(b). The pulse decay time (estimated via exponential fitting), reduces from 14.99 ns to 3.75 ns by increasing R_s from 0Ω to 150Ω without changing the nanowire structure, which is consistent with the analytical expression of τ_2 . However, for a larger value of $R_s = 350 \Omega$, the detector latches to a non-superconducting state, as represented by the temperature profile in Fig. 1(c). In the latter case, the current returns to the SNSPD so rapidly that the resistive spot is sustained by reaching an equilibrium between heat generation via Joule heating in the nanowire and heat dissipation to the substrate. The speed of current redistribution depends on the kinetic inductance of the SNSPD, and thermal interactions are related to the heat transfer coefficient between the nanowire and the substrate. Unfortunately, measuring these properties accurately on different platforms is not straightforward and, therefore, it is non-trivial to predict the maximum R_s which optimizes the current recovery while avoiding the latching or loss of internal efficiency. Using fixed resistors, the experimental testing and validation process can take a considerable amount of effort and time.

Hence, here we propose and demonstrate a cryogenic tunable resistor, as depicted in Fig. 2, which makes it convenient to optimize the SNSPD performance with a serial tunable resistor.

Fig. 2(a) shows the schematic of a tunable resistor. A metal strip (a 80 nm-thick Ti layer with a 5 nm-thick Au layer) is fabricated over a superconducting channel (NbTiN, with a thickness of 8-10 nm) insulated by a thin SiO₂ layer (40-50 nm in thickness). The metal strip acts as a micro-heater once connected to an electric power supply, producing Joule heat and raising the local temperature. When the local temperature exceeds the critical temperature, a resistive strip is formed in the channel, which introduces a tunable resistance in the circuit. The channel is narrowed down as it approaches the center of the metal heater to constrict the expansion of the resistive area and prevent the channel from latching. A typical optical micrograph of a cryogenic tunable resistor is shown in Fig. 2(b).

The resistance of the channel is determined by both the bias current through the superconducting channel I_{ch} , and the heater current I_{h} . In Fig. 2(c), we characterize the dependence of channel resistance R on the currents I_{ch} and I_{h} in the device (DC analysis). The minimum width of the NbTiN channel is 1 μm and the metal heater has a width of 0.1 μm . As the bias current through the superconducting channel increases, the resistance grows faster with the heater current. This behavior is due to the generation of Joule heat in the NbTiN channel $I_{\text{ch}}^2 R$, which becomes significant at higher bias currents. To ensure reliable tunability in the desired resistance range (0 - 300 Ω), the tunable resistor is designed to operate at bias currents much lower than the critical current of the channel, typically around 10 % depending on the heater and the channel geometry as well as the resistivity of the superconducting material.

As depicted in Fig. 2(a), a SNSPD is connected in series with a cryogenic tunable resistor and biased and read out using a conventional bias tee and RF amplifiers. We characterize the sample in flood illumination configuration with light injected from a fiber several centimeters above the sample. The output pulse is amplified and recorded using an oscilloscope. Both the theoretical analysis and the simulation results indicate that a higher I_{h} results in a shorter output pulse duration τ_{out} , allowing two consecutive photons to, in principle, be detected with a shorter time delay. However, another crucial characteristic to consider is the detection efficiency of the second event, which itself depends on not only the current recovery speed but also the degree of saturation of internal detection efficiency (IDE) (i.e., the relative length of the plateau in the detection efficiency curve to the switching current). Since the detection efficiency of SNSPD increases with the effective bias current, the probability of detecting a second photon grows as the current through the

FIG. 2. (a) Illustration of a cryogenic tunable resistor R_s in series with a SNSPD and its electronic readout circuit. (b) Representative optical microscopy image of a cryogenic tunable resistor. (c) Characterization of the channel resistance in a cryogenic tunable resistor as a function of the channel bias current and the heater current. The channel has a width of $1 \mu\text{m}$ and the heater has a width of 100 nm .

SNSPD recovers. Thus, we experimentally measured the recovery of the detection efficiency as a function of the time delay after the first detection event using continuous light sources at different heater currents (i.e., different serial resistances). The time when the efficiency recovers to 50% is defined as the recovery time τ_{rec} .

Fig. 3 shows the experimental results of a SNSPD composed of 70 nm -wide nanowires in series

FIG. 3. (a) Amplified output waveforms of the SNSPD (curves are averaged over 100 sweeps). (b) Recovery of the detection probability after one detection event with various I_h for the wavelength of 1548 nm. The filled dots represent the experimental data, and the solid ones are the predicted efficiency recovery curves derived from internal detection efficiency curves and output pulses. (c) Normalized internal detection efficiency curves with various heater currents I_h , obtained for the wavelength of 1548 nm. (d) Comparison of the output pulse recovery times width τ_{out} (measured at $1/e$ of the pulse amplitude), the experimental recovery time $\tau_{\text{rec,exp}}$, and the derived recovery time $\tau_{\text{rec,der}}$. $\tau_{\text{rec,exp}}$ and $\tau_{\text{rec,der}}$ are obtained by fitting the data with the sigmoid function $y = A(1 + \text{erf}(S(x - x_0)))$.

with a cryogenic tunable resistor with a $1 \mu\text{m}$ -wide channel and a $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ -wide heater. The SNSPD was biased at around 90 % of the switching current and measured at a wavelength of 1548 nm. Fig. 3(a) shows the recorded output pulses for various heater currents I_h . The experimental pulse widths match the trend in the simulation results. As the serial resistance increases by setting a higher heater current, the falling time constant of the output declines from 15.3 ns at $I_h = 0 \mu\text{A}$ to 3.4 ns at $I_h = 74 \mu\text{A}$.

However, the efficiency recovery time does not monotonically decrease as the serial resistance

increases. We experimentally measured the efficiency recovery curve (filled dots) as shown in Fig. 3(b) (More information about the measuring approach can be found in supplementary material section III). Fig. 3(d) shows the comparison between the pulse durations τ_{out} measured from the averaged waveforms in Fig. 3(a), and the experimental recovery time $\tau_{\text{rec,exp}}$ fitted using the experimental efficiency recovery curve in Fig. 3(b). The experimental recovery time $\tau_{\text{rec,exp}}$ is suppressed from 20.3 ns at $I_h = 0 \mu\text{A}$ to 7.1 ns at $I_h = 64 \mu\text{A}$, which is consistent with the declining trend of the output pulse duration. However, the recovery time increases to 7.9 ns at $I_h = 74 \mu\text{A}$ although τ_{out} becomes shorter. Therefore, there is an optimal heater current I_h at $64 \mu\text{A}$, that is, an optimal serial resistance R_s , where the efficiency recovery time can be minimized by reducing the pulse duration.

This results from the degradation of the internal detection efficiency of the detector. Fig. 3(c) shows the internal detection efficiency (IDE) curves as a function of the bias current, which are normalized to the saturated efficiency estimated by fitting to the sigmoid function ($y = A(1 + \text{erf}(S(x - x_0)))$)²³. Since $I_h = 74 \mu\text{A}$ leads to a lower and unsaturated IDE curve, a higher I_d/I_{switch} ratio, which corresponds to a longer delay between two events, is required to achieve the same detection probability. This effect counteracts the influence of the shorter output pulse duration, leading to a worse efficiency recovery time at $I_h = 74 \mu\text{A}$.

The change in the IDE curves is attributed to the decrease of the switching current $I_{\text{switch}} = \min\{I_c, I_{\text{latch}}\}$, where I_c is the critical current determined by the geometry of the nanowire and the critical current density of the superconducting film, and I_{latch} is the latching current at which the resistive spot in the superconducting nanowire is retained. As the output pulse width τ_{out} decreases, I_{latch} declines and eventually drops below I_c .^{19,24} This results in the reduction of I_{switch} , restricting the bias current from approaching the critical current. Consequently, the saturation plateau of the internal detection efficiency diminishes as R_s exceeds an optimal value. The switching current increases slightly at $I_h = 62 \mu\text{A}$, which may result from impedance matching between the tunable resistor and the readout load resistor.

Furthermore, we investigate the recovery of the instantaneous detection efficiency derived from the output pulses and the IDE curve in Fig. 3(a) and (c).²⁵ The instantaneous effective bias current can be estimated using $I_d(t) = I_{\text{bias}} - V_{\text{out}}(t)/G/Z_0$, where $V_{\text{out}}(t)$ is the output pulse and $G = 10^{2.9}$ is the measured gain of our amplifier. Combined with the IDE curve $\eta = f(I_d)$, the instantaneous detection efficiency can be derived as $\eta(t) = f(I_d(t))$, which is shown as solid lines in Fig. 3(b). The derived recovery time $\tau_{\text{rec,der}}$ is determined using sigmoidal fitting and plotted in Fig. 3(d).

Discrepancies between $\tau_{\text{rec,der}}$ and $\tau_{\text{rec,exp}}$ are probably caused by inaccurate estimations of effective bias currents, and the triggering threshold for the second detection event (hysteresis settings of counter's Schmitt trigger), which omits some events because of their lower amplitude or background noise (see more details in supplementary material section III). Nevertheless, $\tau_{\text{rec,der}}$ and $\tau_{\text{rec,exp}}$ show similar tendencies with respect to I_h , and exhibit good agreement under conditions of rapid efficiency recovery. Therefore, analyzing $\tau_{\text{rec,der}}$ can be considered as a time-efficient approach to optimize the serial tunable resistor.

In order to further investigate the effect of recovery time reduction, we characterize the SNSPD

FIG. 4. Normalized detection efficiency as a function of detection count rates at various heater currents I_h with a repetition rate of (a) $f_{\text{rep}} = 50$ MHz and (b) $f_{\text{rep}} = 120$ MHz. For each laser repetition rate, the best detector performance can be achieved by tuning the heater current. Measurements at $I_h = 64 \mu\text{A}$, which consistently delivers near-optimal or optimal performances across a broad range of count rates, are highlighted with triangles for a better display.

detection efficiency at high count rates illuminated with a pulsed light source at 1548 nm at different heater currents. The detection efficiency, for each input photon flux, is calculated using the count rates at 95% of the switching current. Examples of the measurement curves (count rate versus bias current at different input photon fluxes) are presented in supplementary material section IV. The analyzed results of are shown in Fig. 4 for the laser repetition rates of 50 MHz and 120 MHz. Note that the data in Fig. 4 is normalized with respect to the efficiency at for the lowest input photon flux (lowest count rate) when $I_h = 0 \mu\text{A}$ (more measurements at different repetition rates can be found in supplementary material).

According to the measurement in Fig. 3(d), the recovery time of the SNSPD is longer or comparable to $1/f_{\text{rep}}$ at lower heater currents than $60 \mu\text{A}$. Thus, the detection efficiencies for these

lower heater currents decrease as the count rate increases (due to the insufficient current recovery through the SNSPD). When the count rates increase beyond half of f_{rep} , the efficiency exhibits an upward tendency, which is attributed to the increase of SNSPD current via parasitic discharging currents of the readout capacitor.²⁶ The parasitic currents flowing back through the SNSPD enhance the effective bias currents and thus the detection efficiency.

As the heater current increases, the best efficiency performance over a broad range of count rates is achieved at $I_h = 64 \mu\text{A}$, which is in accordance with the recovery time measurement. When the heater current exceeds $64 \mu\text{A}$, the efficiency declines steadily due to the unsaturated IDE (see supplementary material Fig. S4). At $f_{\text{rep}} = 50 \text{ MHz}$ and $I_h = 64 \mu\text{A}$, the detection efficiency is maintained around the highest level at various count rates, since the minimal time delay between two pulses, which is 20 ns , is significantly longer than the recovery time $\tau_{\text{rec,exp}} = 7.1 \text{ ns}$, resulting in complete recovery of the effective bias current for all detection events. As the minimum separation between incident photons for the case of $f_{\text{rep}} = 120 \text{ MHz}$ approaches the recovery time (at $I_h = 64 \mu\text{A}$), and the efficiency recovery is not fully completed, a slight decline in efficiency can be observed at higher count rates.

In conclusion, we demonstrated a cryogenic tunable resistor controlled by the localized micro-heater. The device is intrinsically cryogenic-compatible and suitable for integration with other superconducting devices. We showed that, by controlling the tunable resistor in series with a SNSPD, the efficiency recovery time of the detector can be tuned to enhance detection efficiency at high count rates. Compared with trial-and-error-based fixed resistive networks, the cryogenic tunable resistor significantly speeds up the optimization process and can be adapted to a variety of SNSPD geometries or materials. Our solution provides a convenient method to tune SNSPD performance at higher photon fluxes. In addition, the tunable resistor presented here has the potential to be integrated with other cryogenic technologies.

See the supplementary material for details on sample fabrication, electro-thermal simulation of SNSPDs, the approach to measure the efficiency recovery, and more results of high-count-rate measurements.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Hui Wang: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (lead); Methodology (equal); Resources (equal); Software (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Nikita Dmitrievič Orlov:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Niels Noordzij:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Resources (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Thomas Descamps:** Investigation (equal); Resources (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **J. W. Niels Los:** Conceptualization (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Val Zwiller:** Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Iman Esmaeil Zadeh:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the authors.

REFERENCES

- ¹G. N. Gol'tsman, O. Okunev, G. Chulkova, A. Lipatov, A. Semenov, K. Smirnov, B. Voronov, A. Dzardanov, C. Williams, and R. Sobolewski, "Picosecond superconducting single-photon optical detector," *Applied Physics Letters* **79**, 705–707 (2001), https://pubs.aip.org/aip/apl/article-pdf/79/6/705/8782545/705_1_online.pdf.
- ²J. A. Lau, V. B. Verma, D. Schwarzer, and A. M. Wodtke, "Superconducting single-photon detectors in the mid-infrared for physical chemistry and spectroscopy," *Chemical Society Reviews* **52**, 921–941 (2023).
- ³F. P. Venza and M. Colangelo, "Research trends in single-photon detectors based on superconducting wires," *APL Photonics* **10** (2025), 10.1063/5.0246490.
- ⁴Y. Pan, H. Zhou, X. Zhang, H. Yu, L. Zhang, M. Si, H. Li, L. You, and Z. Wang, "Mid-infrared nb4n3-based superconducting nanowire single photon detectors for wavelengths up to 10 μm ," *Optics Express* **30**, 40044–40052 (2022).
- ⁵M. Colangelo, A. B. Walter, B. A. Korzh, E. Schmidt, B. Bumble, A. E. Lita, A. D. Beyer, J. P. Allmaras, R. M. Briggs, A. G. Kozorezov, E. E. Wollman, M. D. Shaw, and K. K. Berggren, "Large-area superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors for operation at wavelengths up to 7.4 μm ," *Nano Letters* **22**, 5667–5673 (2022), PMID: 35848767, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.1c05012>.
- ⁶J. Chang, J. W. N. Los, J. O. Tenorio-Pearl, N. Noordzij, R. Gourgues, A. Guardiani, J. R. Zichi, S. F. Pereira, H. P. Urbach, V. Zwiller, S. N. Dorenbos, and I. Esmail Zadeh, "Detecting telecom single photons with $\left(99.5^{+0.5}_{-2.07}\right)\%$ system detection efficiency and high time resolution," *APL Photonics* **6**, 036114 (2021).
- ⁷D. V. Reddy, R. R. Nerem, S. W. Nam, R. P. Mirin, and V. B. Verma, "Superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors with 98% system detection efficiency at 1550 nm," *Optica* **7**, 1649–1653 (2020).
- ⁸P. Hu, H. Li, L. You, H. Wang, Y. Xiao, J. Huang, X. Yang, W. Zhang, Z. Wang, and X. Xie, "Detecting single infrared photons toward optimal system detection efficiency," *Opt. Express*

- 28**, 36884–36891 (2020).
- ⁹B. Korzh, Q.-Y. Zhao, J. P. Allmaras, S. Frasca, T. M. Autry, E. A. Bersin, A. D. Beyer, R. M. Briggs, B. Bumble, M. Colangelo, G. M. Crouch, A. E. Dane, T. Gerrits, A. E. Lita, F. Marsili, G. Moody, C. Peña, E. Ramirez, J. D. Rezac, N. Sinclair, M. J. Stevens, A. E. Velasco, V. B. Verma, E. E. Wollman, S. Xie, D. Zhu, P. D. Hale, M. Spiropulu, K. L. Silverman, R. P. Mirin, S. W. Nam, A. G. Kozorezov, M. D. Shaw, and K. K. Berggren, “Demonstration of sub-3 ps temporal resolution with a superconducting nanowire single-photon detector,” *Nature Photonics* **14**, 250–255 (2020).
- ¹⁰G. G. Taylor, E. N. MacKenzie, B. Korzh, D. V. Morozov, B. Bumble, A. D. Beyer, J. P. Allmaras, M. D. Shaw, and R. H. Hadfield, “Mid-infrared timing jitter of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors,” *Applied Physics Letters* **121**, 214001 (2022).
- ¹¹J. Chang, I. E. Zadeh, J. W. N. Los, J. Zichi, A. Fognini, M. Gevers, S. Dorenbos, S. F. Pereira, P. Urbach, and V. Zwiller, “Multimode-fiber-coupled superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors with high detection efficiency and time resolution,” *Applied Optics* **58**, 9803–9807 (2019).
- ¹²F. Xia, M. Gevers, A. Fognini, A. T. Mok, B. Li, N. Akbari, I. E. Zadeh, J. Qin-Dregely, and C. Xu, “Short-wave infrared confocal fluorescence imaging of deep mouse brain with a superconducting nanowire single-photon detector,” *ACS Photonics* **8**, 2800–2810 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsp Photonics.1c01018>.
- ¹³F. Bellei, A. P. Cartwright, A. N. McCaughan, A. E. Dane, F. Najafi, Q. Zhao, and K. K. Berggren, “Free-space-coupled superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors for infrared optical communications,” *Opt. Express* **24**, 3248–3257 (2016).
- ¹⁴K. Takemoto, Y. Nambu, T. Miyazawa, Y. Sakuma, T. Yamamoto, S. Yorozu, and Y. Arakawa, “Quantum key distribution over 120km using ultrahigh purity single-photon source and superconducting single-photon detectors,” *Scientific Reports* **5**, 14383 (2015).
- ¹⁵F. Grünenfelder, A. Boaron, G. V. Resta, M. Perrenoud, D. Rusca, C. Barreiro, R. Houlmann, R. Sax, L. Stasi, S. El-Khoury, E. Hänggi, N. Bosshard, F. Bussièrès, and H. Zbinden, “Fast single-photon detectors and real-time key distillation enable high secret-key-rate quantum key distribution systems,” *Nature Photonics* **17**, 422–426 (2023).
- ¹⁶F. Beutel, H. Gehring, M. A. Wolff, C. Schuck, and W. Pernice, “Detector-integrated on-chip qkd receiver for ghz clock rates,” *npj Quantum Information* **7**, 40 (2021).

- ¹⁷D.-K. Liu, S.-J. Chen, L.-X. You, Y.-L. Wang, S. Miki, Z. Wang, X.-M. Xie, and M.-H. Jiang, “Nonlatching superconducting nanowire single-photon detection with quasi-constant-voltage bias,” *Applied Physics Express* **5** (2012), 10.1143/apex.5.125202.
- ¹⁸Q. Zhao, T. Jia, M. Gu, C. Wan, L. Zhang, W. Xu, L. Kang, J. Chen, and P. Wu, “Counting rate enhancements in superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors with improved readout circuits,” *Opt. Lett.* **39**, 1869–1872 (2014).
- ¹⁹A. J. Kerman, D. Rosenberg, R. J. Molnar, and E. A. Dauler, “Readout of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors at high count rates,” *Journal of Applied Physics* **113**, 144511 (2013), https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jap/article-pdf/doi/10.1063/1.4799397/13212532/144511_1_online.pdf.
- ²⁰C. L. Lv, H. Zhou, H. Li, L. X. You, X. Y. Liu, Y. Wang, W. J. Zhang, S. J. Chen, Z. Wang, and X. M. Xie, “Large active area superconducting single-nanowire photon detector with a 100 μm diameter,” *Superconductor Science and Technology* **30**, 115018 (2017).
- ²¹J. K. W. Yang, A. J. Kerman, E. A. Dauler, V. Anant, K. M. Rosfjord, and K. K. Berggren, “Modeling the electrical and thermal response of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors,” *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity* **17**, 581–585 (2007).
- ²²A. J. Kerman, J. K. W. Yang, R. J. Molnar, E. A. Dauler, and K. K. Berggren, “Electrothermal feedback in superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors,” *Physical Review B* **79** (2009), 10.1103/PhysRevB.79.100509.
- ²³C. Autebert, G. Gras, E. Amri, M. Perrenoud, M. Caloz, H. Zbinden, and F. Bussieres, “Direct measurement of the recovery time of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors,” *Journal of Applied Physics* **128** (2020), 10.1063/5.0007976.
- ²⁴I. Craiciu, B. Korzh, A. D. Beyer, A. Mueller, J. P. Allmaras, L. Narvez, M. Spiropulu, B. Bumble, T. Lehner, E. E. Wollman, and M. D. Shaw, “High-speed detection of 1550 nm single photons with superconducting nanowire detectors,” *Optica* **10**, 183–190 (2023).
- ²⁵L. Oshiro, H. Jones, T. Rambo, J. Cassada, S. Boyd, and A. Miller, “Accurately modeling the recovery time of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors as a function of bias current,” in *Quantum Computing, Communication, and Simulation V*, Vol. 13391, edited by P. R. Hemmer and A. L. Migdall, International Society for Optics and Photonics (SPIE, 2025) p. 133910Z.
- ²⁶S. Ferrari, V. Kovalyuk, A. Vetter, C. Lee, C. Rockstuhl, A. Semenov, G. Gol’tsman, and W. Pernice, “Analysis of the detection response of waveguide-integrated superconducting

nanowire single-photon detectors at high count rate,” *Applied Physics Letters* **115** (2019), 10.1063/1.5113652.

Supplementary material: Controlling the recovery time of the superconducting nanowire single-photon detector with a low-power and voltage-controlled cryogenic tunable resistor

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I. SAMPLE FABRICATION

The deposition of NbTiN films is carried out on thermally oxidized silicon wafers in magnetron cosputtering in Ar and N₂ atmosphere. The film thickness is around 10 nm, corresponding to the critical temperature at around 8~10 K (see Gourgues *et al.*¹). Next, the gold contact pads and markers are patterned using electron-beam lithography (EBL, 100 kV acceleration) with a double-layer PMMA resist. After development in a 1:3 MIBK:IPA solution, a 5-nm Cr sticking layer and a 55-nm Au layer are deposited via electron-beam metal evaporation. Lift-off is then carried out in acetone at 45 °C. Afterwards, NbTiN patterns are created with EBL using the positive resist ARP6200.4 and developed in pentyl acetate. The NbTiN structures are later etched using reactive ion etching (RIE) with an SF₆/O₂ plasma. SiO₂ insulating structures are then patterned using a positive resist ARP6200.9. After deposition of a 30~40 nm-thick SiO₂ layer in inductively coupled plasma chemical vapor deposition (ICPCVD) at 150 °C, the structures are lifted off in PRS-3000. Finally, the metal heaters are fabricated through another lift-off process using double-layer PMMA resist. They are composed of a 80 nm-thick Ti layer and a 5 nm-thick Au layer deposited using electron-beam metal evaporation.

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FIG. S1. (a) and (b) Hysteresis I_h - R measurement of a cryogenic tunable resistor with I_h sweeping in the (a) increasing, and (b) decreasing direction. The NbTiN channel is 1 μm wide and the heater is 100 nm wide. (c) The switching heating current (I_h^+) and the retrap current (I_h^-) of the NbTiN channel obtained from the results in (a) and (b).

II. ELECTRO-THERMAL SIMULATION OF SNSPDS

We conduct a 1D electro-thermal simulation of a SNSPD with a width of $w = 70$ nm and a length of $l = 525$ μm using the coupled electro-thermal differential equation described by Yang *et al.*². The equivalent electrical circuit of the simulation is shown in Fig. 1(a). The coupled electrothermal equations are expressed as²

$$\begin{cases} J^2 \cdot \rho + \kappa \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\alpha}{d} (T - T_{\text{sub}}) = \frac{\partial cT}{\partial t}, & (1) \\ C_b \left(\frac{d^2 L_k I}{dt^2} + \frac{d(IR_L)}{dt} + (Z_0 + R_S) \frac{dI}{dt} \right) = I_{\text{bias}} - I. & (2) \end{cases}$$

In the thermal differential equation (Equation 1), J is the current density, ρ is the resistivity, κ is the thermal conductivity of the superconducting film, α is the thermal boundary conductivity between the superconducting film and the substrate, d is the film thickness, T_{sub} is the base temperature, and c is the heat capacity of the superconducting material.

In the electrical differential equation (Equation 2), $C_b = 100$ nF is the capacitance, L_k is the kinetic inductance of the SNSPD, R_L is the resistance of the SNSPD, $Z_0 = 50$ Ω is the load resistor in readout electronics, and R_S is the serial resistance. Equation 1 and 2 are discretized using the Crank-Nicolson method and then solved as a tridiagonal-matrix problem in MATLAB.

The film properties used in the simulation are derived from either literature or experimental data. The film thickness is approximated as $d = 10$ nm and the critical temperature is assumed as

$T_c = 10$ K. The base temperature is set to $T_{\text{sub}} = 2.5$ K. The sheet resistance and the sheet inductance of the NbTiN film are estimated as $R_d = \rho/d = 300 \text{ } \Omega/\square$ and $L_{k,d} = 100 \text{ pH}/\square$. Therefore, the kinetic inductance of the SNSPD is $L_k = L_{k,d}l/w = 750 \text{ nH}$. The critical current of the SNSPD follows

$$I_c(T) = I_c(T = 0) \left(1 - \left(\frac{T}{T_c} \right)^2 \right)^2, \quad (3)$$

where $I_c(T = 0)$ is estimated as $13.13 \text{ } \mu\text{A}$ (which is derived from the experimental critical current $I_c(T = T_{\text{sub}}) = 12.1 \text{ } \mu\text{A}$). The SNSPD is biased with $I_{\text{bias}} = 0.9I_c(T = T_{\text{sub}}) = 10.89 \text{ } \mu\text{A}$ in the simulation.

The thermal conductivity κ relies on both the state and the temperature, which can be described as

$$\kappa(T) = \begin{cases} LT/\rho, & \text{in normal state,} \\ \frac{T}{T_c} \kappa(T_c) = \frac{LT^2}{T_c \rho}, & \text{in superconducting state,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $L = 2.45 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W } \Omega \text{ K}^{-2}$ is the Lorenz number.

The thermal boundary conductivity α between the substrate and the NbTiN film depends on the temperature, i.e. $\alpha = BT^3$, according to the literature.² When a hot spot can be maintained in the nanostructure, Equation 1 can be rewritten as³

$$\alpha(T = T_c^*) = \frac{J_{\text{retrap}}^2 d \rho}{T_c^* - T_{\text{sub}}} = \frac{I_{\text{retrap}}^2 R_d}{w^2 (T_c^* - T_{\text{sub}})}, \quad (5)$$

where T_c^* can be derived from the switching current (i.e., the bias current where the superconducting state is about to break) and the retrapping current (i.e., the bias current where the device cannot recover from the resistive state to the superconducting state)

$$\begin{cases} I_{\text{retrap}} = I_c(T = 0) \left(1 - \left(\frac{T_c^*}{T_c} \right)^2 \right)^2, \\ I_{\text{switch}} = I_c(T = 0) \left(1 - \left(\frac{T_{\text{sub}}}{T_c} \right)^2 \right)^2. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

We measured the hysteresis of a cryogenic tunable resistor (with a $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ wide superconducting channel and a 100-nm wide metal heater) to estimate the parameter B using Equation 5 and 6. As shown in Fig. S1 (a) and (b), the heater current was swept in ascending or descending order while maintaining the same bias current through the superconducting channel. When there is no heater current, the device can be switched to a non-superconducting state at $I_{\text{switch}} \approx 192 \text{ } \mu\text{A}$, and be trapped in a resistive state at $I_{\text{retrap}} \approx 36 \text{ } \mu\text{A}$. By solving Equation 5 and Equation 6, we can

obtain $\alpha(T = T_c^*) \approx 68.89 \times 10^3 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ and $T_c^* \approx 7.707 \text{ K}$. Thus, $B = \alpha(T = T_c^*)/(T_c^*)^3 \approx 102.8 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-4}$.

c is the heat capacity of the NbTiN film, which is defined as

$$c = c_e + c_{\text{ph}} \quad (7)$$

where c_e is the electron heat capacity and c_{ph} is the phonon heat capacity. They are calculated using the following expressions:

$$c_e = \begin{cases} \gamma T, & \text{in normal state,} \\ Ae^{-\Delta(T)/k_B T}, & \text{in superconducting state.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and

$$c_{\text{ph}} = c_{\text{ph}0} T^3. \quad (9)$$

The superconducting energy gap is estimated with the following expression⁴

$$\Delta(T) = 1.76 k_B T_c \tanh\left(\frac{\pi}{1.76} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \times 1.43 \left(\frac{T_c}{T} - 1\right)}\right), \quad (10)$$

where $k_B \approx 1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ JK}^{-1}$ is the Boltzmann constant. $\gamma \approx 151.5 \text{ Jm}^{-3} \text{ K}^2$ and $c_{\text{ph}0} \approx 12.849 \text{ Jm}^{-3} \text{ K}^4$ are estimated from the reported data of the 9-nm NbTiN film in Sidorova *et al.*⁵ According to the literature, $A = 2.43 \gamma T_c$.⁶

III. EFFICIENCY RECOVERY MEASUREMENT

In this work, we experimentally measure the efficiency recovery using continuous laser sources. Following the Poissonian statistics of photon distribution from laser sources, the probability of a subsequent photon incidence is independent of the time interval between two photons. Therefore, the distribution of the delay time between two detection events reflects the time-dependent recovery of the detection efficiency after one detection event. As Fig. S2 shows, rising edges across certain trigger level are recognized by an oscilloscope (Teledyne LeCroy WaveRunner 640Zi). The time difference between two successive rising slopes at the trigger level is measured as the delay time. Since the second pulse detected after a shorter delay has a lower amplitude due to the partially recovered bias current, the trigger level is empirically set to 60% of the first pulse amplitude. To rule out errors induced by electrical noises or fluctuations, we set a hysteresis band

of ± 35 mV around the trigger level. Over 200,000 measurements are acquired and stored as a histogram (as Fig. 3(b) shows) by the oscilloscope.

FIG. S2. Schematic of the delay time measurement on the output waveform of two successive detection events.

IV. HIGH-COUNT-RATE MEASUREMENTS

In high-count-rate measurements, the incident photon rate could exceed a hundred megahertz, which is higher than $1/\tau_{\text{out}}$. Due to the lack of photon-number-resolving capability, comparing the measured photon count rate with the incident photon rate under continuous light illumination can result in an overestimation or underestimation of the detection efficiency. Therefore, we employ the following method to evaluate the detection efficiency at high count rates using a pulsed laser.

The laser pulses are generated by modulating a laser diode output with an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG). The pulse duration is set to be around 3.3 ns, which is limited by the AWG settings. Since it is substantially shorter than the recovery time, only one event can be triggered per optical pulse despite potential multi-photon absorption. Rather than counting the amount of detected photons, we determine the detection efficiency of the SNSPD η from the possibility that zero photon is detected in one optical pulse.

According to the Poisson distribution, the possibility to have n photons in a pulse can be expressed as

$$P(n) = \frac{\mu^n}{n!} e^{-\mu}, \quad (11)$$

where μ is the average number of photons in a pulse. The average number of photons is calculated using

$$\mu = \frac{\lambda P_{\text{in}}}{hc f_{\text{rep}}}, \quad (12)$$

where λ is the laser wavelength, P_{in} is the input laser power, $h \approx 6.62607 \times 10^{-34} \text{ JHz}^{-1}$ is the Planck constant, and $c \approx 2.99792 \times 10^9 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ is the speed of light. Firstly, the possibility where the number of detection events d for an optical pulse equals 0 can be described analytically as

$$\begin{aligned} P(d=0) &= P(n=0) + P(n \neq 0)(1-\eta)^n \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\text{inf}} P(n)(1-\eta)^n \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\text{inf}} \frac{\mu^n}{n!} e^{-\mu} (1-\eta)^n \\ &= e^{-\eta\mu}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Second, $P(d=0)$ can also be obtained from the experimental result, which is written as

$$P(d=0) = 1 - \frac{\text{PCR}}{f_{\text{rep}}}, \quad (14)$$

where PCR is the photon count rate measured by the SNSPD and f_{rep} is the repetition rate of the pulsed laser. Combining Eq. 14 and Eq. 13, we can derive that

$$\eta = -\frac{\ln(1 - \frac{\text{PCR}}{f_{\text{rep}}})}{\mu}. \quad (15)$$

By applying various attenuation levels on the input laser source, we measure sets of count-rate curves versus bias currents, as shown in Fig. S3. Count rates at 95 % of the switching currents are used to derive the relationship between detection efficiencies and count rates in Fig. 4 and S4 at different repetition rates. Since the selected count rate might fall on the unsaturated region due to the decline of switching current, the calculated efficiency can fluctuate or decrease as the region highlighted by dashed circles for $I_{\text{h}} = 80 \mu\text{A}$ and $I_{\text{h}} = 120 \mu\text{A}$ in Fig. S4 (c) and (d) shows. Similar to the analysis of Fig. 4, the detection efficiency at high count rates is substantially improved at I_{h} around 64 μA , which is consistent with the result of efficiency recovery measurements. The measured optimal heater current slightly shifts for $f_{\text{rep}} = 80 \text{ MHz}$, which can be caused by incident power drift during experiments due to laser power fluctuations or fiber instability. The normalized detection efficiency exceeding unity at high count rates can be due to multiple detection events within one laser pulse or oscillations caused by the parasitic discharging current of the readout capacitor.

FIG. S3. Relationship between bias currents and count rates at various attenuations of light and heater currents I_h with a repetition rate of (a) $f_{\text{rep}} = 120 \text{ MHz}$ and (b) $f_{\text{rep}} = 50 \text{ MHz}$. Black crosses indicate the count rates at 95 % of the switching current, which are used to calculate detection efficiencies in Fig. S4.

FIG. S4. Normalized detection efficiency as a function of detection count rates at various heater currents I_h with a repetition rate of (a) $f_{\text{rep}} = 50$ MHz, (b) $f_{\text{rep}} = 80$ MHz, (c) $f_{\text{rep}} = 100$ MHz, and (d) $f_{\text{rep}} = 120$ MHz. Measurements at the optimal heater currents are marked as triangles for each repetition rate. Data within the dashed circles is caused by the unsaturated internal detection efficiency (IDE).

REFERENCES

- ¹R. Gourgues, J. W. N. Los, J. Zichi, J. Chang, N. Kalhor, G. Bulgarini, S. N. Dorenbos, V. Zwiller, and I. E. Zadeh, “Superconducting nanowire single photon detectors operating at temperature from 4 to 7 k,” *Optics Express* **27**, 24601–24609 (2019).
- ²J. K. W. Yang, A. J. Kerman, E. A. Dauler, V. Anant, K. M. Rosfjord, and K. K. Berggren, “Modeling the electrical and thermal response of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors,” *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity* **17**, 581–585 (2007).
- ³A. Dane, J. Allmaras, D. Zhu, M. Onen, M. Colangelo, R. Baghdadi, J.-L. Tambasco, Y. Morimoto, I. E. Forno, I. Charaev, Q. Zhao, M. Skvortsov, A. Kozorezov, and K. K. Berggren, “Self-heating hotspots in superconducting nanowires cooled by phonon black-body radiation,” *Nature Communications* **13**, 5429 (2022).
- ⁴F. Gross, B. S. Chandrasekhar, D. Einzel, K. Andres, P. J. Hirschfeld, H. R. Ott, J. Beuers, Z. Fisk, and J. L. Smith, “Anomalous temperature dependence of the magnetic field penetration depth in superconducting Nb_3Sn ,” *Zeitschrift für Physik B Condensed Matter* **64**, 175–188 (1986).
- ⁵M. Sidorova, A. D. Semenov, H.-W. Hübers, S. Gyger, and S. Steinhauer, “Phonon heat capacity and self-heating normal domains in NbTiN nanostrips,” *Superconductor Science and Technology* **35**, 105005 (2022).
- ⁶M. Tinkham, *Introduction to Superconductivity*, Dover Books on Physics Series (Dover Publications, 2004).